

Refining the identification criteria for *forma typica* and *brachycerca* in exuviae of *Boyeria irene* (Odonata: Aeshnidae)

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Abstract. In female imagines of *Boyeria irene*, two forms are known according to the length of the cerci: *forma brachycerca* (short appendages) and *f. typica* (long appendages). Both forms are also recognisable in exuviae. Hitherto, no accurate measurements have been performed to distinguish between the two forms. Hence, we measured and analysed the absolute and relative length of the cerci in both sexes of exuviae from 11 populations originating from the centre and north of the Iberian Peninsula. We show that there are specimens intermediate between the two forms and that dimorphism is also present in males. The *brachycerca* form is more frequent in the north than in the centre of the Iberian Peninsula. Correct identification of both forms should always be based on accurate measurements of the length of the cerci.

Further key words. Dragonfly, Anisoptera, rivers, Iberian Peninsula, Spain, Portugal

Introduction

Numerous odonate species show intersexual differences in size, colour, behaviour, etc. (CROWLEY & JOHANSSON 2002), but intrasexual variation is

likewise prevalent (e.g., FINCKE et al. 2005; SCHNEIDER & WILDERMUTH 2009; KHAN & HERBERSTEIN 2019; WILDERMUTH & MONNERAT 2020). Some variable morphological traits may coincide with genetic differences within the population (VAN GOSSUM et al. 2008; PILGRIM et al. 2002), although this is not always the case (HUANG et al. 2020).

Boyeria irene (Fonscolombe, 1838) is a large anisopteran (body length 63–67 mm; ASKEW 2004) mainly distributed in the western Mediterranean (BOUDOT et al. 2015), where it usually lives in mountain streams. In females, but not in males, dimorphism in the abdominal appendages of adults and larvae has been described (NAVÁS 1919; WENGER 1959), so that two forms can be distinguished: *forma brachycerca* (short appendages) and *f. typica* (long appendages). In studies of this dimorphism (e.g., ROBERT 1958; WENGER 1959; AGUESSE 1968; VICK 1984; JACQUEMIN 1985; PETERS 1987; MIKOLAJEWSKI et al. 2000; BROCHARD 2018) the separation of forms has been based on biometric criteria, either the total length of the appendages in adults or the length of the cerci relative to that of the paraproct in larvae and exuviae.

The biology of the *B. irene* larva is well known (WILDERMUTH 2005), as is its biometry in the various instars of larval development (FERRERAS-ROMERO 1997). However, the size of the cerci in larvae and exuviae of the forms *brachycerca* and *typica* has not yet been properly established and so there is no reliable criterion to allow their identification. Moreover, no intermediate forms have been described so far and in the Iberian Peninsula the proportion of the two forms is still not known, because this trait has only been quantified in a few populations (FERRERAS-ROMERO & SUHLING 2021). FERRERAS-ROMERO & SUHLING (2021) have reviewed the data on this dimorphism in a population from southern Iberia in which the *brachycerca* form is in the majority, while the percentage of specimens of the *typica* form decreases as the larval emergence period progresses.

Identification of the *typica* and *brachycerca* forms based on the cercus length (CEL) / paraproct length (PAL) ratio eliminates the influence of body size, while identification based on the length of the cercus (CEL) is simple and efficient. In this study we analyse exuviae collected over a wide area of their distribution. The main topic of the study was to make accurate measurements of the cerci in *f. brachycerca* and in *f. typica* to find out whether there

is a clear separation between the two – that is, whether two discrete groups exist. Based on this data, it is also possible to establish whether the proportion of these two forms is uniform in the study area. In the Iberian Peninsula, *B. irene* is widespread (BOUDOT et al. 2015). It is important to determine precisely which forms are present in each sex and how many individuals of each form are present within a population because this helps to estimate the degree of genetic diversity (SADEGHI et al. 2010; KOHLI et al. 2018).

Material and methods

In the north-western half of the Iberian Peninsula, two main mountain ranges are present (Fig. 1): the Cantabrian Mountains, parallel to the coast of the Cantabrian Sea, from the Bay of Biscay to the Atlantic Ocean, and the

Figure 1. Rivers sampled in the Cantabrian Mountains (CM) and Central System (CS) of the Iberian Peninsula: 1 – Cova; 2 – Tuela; 3 – Sabor; 4 – Zêzere; 5 – Frío; 6 – Agadón; 7 – Ladrillar; 8 – Francia; 9 – Tormes; 10 – Alberche; 11 – Eresma. Shaded area: elevation > 1000 m a.s.l.

Table 1. Some characteristics of the sampled rivers of this study: CM – Cantabrian Mountains. CS – Central System; N, W – coordinates in decimal degrees; El – elevation [m a.s.l.]; Tm: mean annual temperature [°C]; Pre: annual precipitation [mm].

System	River	Mountain range	N	W	El	Tm	Pre
CM	1. Cova	Tras-os-Montes	41.589166	-7.798611	329	12.9	1110
CM	2. Tuela	Tras-os-Montes	41.810555	-6.994722	457	12.0	1025
CM	3. Sabor	Tras-os-Montes	41.902500	-6.736388	665	11.8	1087
CS	4. Zêzere	Serra da Estrela	40.142212	-7.448495	559	12.7	1429
CS	5. Frío	Sierra de Gata	40.322534	-6.645508	830	12.6	1044
CS	6. Agadón	Sierra de Gata	40.433702	-6.331277	760	12.8	777
CS	7. Ladrillar	Sierra de Francia	40.412519	-6.097150	417	15.3	1138
CS	8. Francia	Sierra de Francia	40.485840	-6.006844	545	14.7	946
CS	9. Tormes	Sierra de Gredos	40.334598	-5.349011	1120	11.2	691
CS	10. Alberche	Sierra de Piedrahíta	40.387423	-4.923627	1150	11.2	1021
CS	11. Eresma	Sierra de Guadarrama	40.860445	-4.027662	1200	10.4	835

Central System, a range *ca* 500 km long that crosses the peninsula from East to West. Three rivers in northern Portugal, at the south-western end of the Cantabrian Mountains, and eight rivers in the Central System were sampled. Sample sites were characterised according to elevation (metres a.s.l.) according to the official website of Spanish National Geographic Institute (www.ign.es), annual precipitation and annual mean temperature (NINYE-ROLA et al. 2005; Table 1).

Exuviae of *Boyeria irene* were collected by two researchers by carefully inspecting all substrates (soil, emergent vegetation, stones, tree trunks, logs, etc.) located in the riverbanks, in July and August of the years 2015 to 2020. All exuviae were preserved dry and identified according to DOUCET (2010). Sex determination was done according to the presence (female) or absence (male) of gonapophyses on the ventral surface of abdominal segment 8. Two measurements were taken in those exuviae collected: cercus length (CEL) and paraproct length (PAL), both according to DOUCET (2010). These variables were measured to the nearest 0.1 mm, using a binocular stereomicroscope with an eyepiece micrometer.

CEL and PAL were used to identify forms *brachycerca* and *typica* according to two criteria:

(i) CEL, only in the case where the values of this variable form two discrete groups.

(ii) CEL/PAL ratio. ROBERT (1958) proposed that in *forma brachycerca* and *f. typica*, cercus is $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{3}{5}$ of the paraproct length, respectively, and this criterion was followed by ASKEW (2004) and FERRERAS-ROMERO & SUHLING (2021). VICK (1984) proposed that when CEL is less than half of PAL, the specimen is *brachycerca*, and when it is greater than half it belongs to the *typica* form.

Absolute frequencies of the exuviae of the two forms were compared by chi-square test (χ^2), with Yates's correction where necessary (one degree of freedom). Correlation between the percentage of *brachycerca* for exuviae and environmental variables was done using Spearman's correlation coefficient. These calculations were performed in PAST 3.15 (HAMMER et al. 2001).

Results

A total of 1 776 exuviae were collected (767 males, 1 009 females), of which 1 367 originated from the Central System (605 males, 762 females) and 409 from northern Portugal (162 males, 247 females).

Identification of *forma brachycerca* and *f. typica*

In female exuviae the CEL value ranged from 0.80 to 2.45 mm. The distribution of specimens according to CEL shows a gap at 1.5 mm (Fig. 2), so that it could be established that exuviae with $CEL < 1.5$ mm belong to the *brachycerca* form and those with $CEL > 1.5$ mm belong to the *typica* form. In this case, there would be 946 *brachycerca* exuviae (93.8 % of the total) and 63 *typica* exuviae.

In female exuviae the value of the CEL/PAL ratio ranged from 0.22 to 0.67. There were 946 exuviae with $CEL/PAL \leq 0.37$ (i.e., about one third) and all belonged to the *brachycerca* form calculated according to the CEL criterion. Therefore, the criteria match completely. Applying VICK's (1984) criterion, 25 exuviae (39.7 % of those identified as *typica* applying the above criterion) should be identified as *brachycerca* (ratio 0.39–0.50) and 38 as *typica* (ratio > 0.50).

In male exuviae the CEL value ranged from 1.00 to 2.60 mm, higher values than those obtained in female exuviae. The distribution by length class varied markedly between sexes (Fig. 2): in males, 98.3 % of the exuviae had CEL > 1.5 mm, and a small but significant percentage (1.7%) had CEL < 1.5 mm. Therefore, if we apply the same criterion as in females, these exuviae should also be considered as *brachycerca*.

Figure 2. Number of male and female exuviae of *Boyeria irene* according to the cercus length [mm]. Arrow indicates the separation of *brachycerca* and *typica* forms.

In male exuviae the value of the CEL/PAL ratio ranged from 0.26 to 0.68, similar to that of the females. There were 749 exuviae with CEL/PAL ≥ 0.37 and all had CEL > 1.5 mm, which meant that they could be identified as *typica* exuviae. In all those identified as *brachycerca* (n = 13) the value of this ratio ranged from 0.26 to 0.37. Furthermore, five exuviae (0.65 % of all males) had CEL = 1.5 mm with CEL/PAL values between 0.38 and 0.43 which, consequently, makes it difficult to assign them to either of the two forms.

Geographical variation

The percentage of female exuviae of the *typica* form was significantly higher in Central System rivers than in Cantabrian Mountains rivers (10.0 and 0.8 %, respectively; $\chi^2 = 18.116$, 1 d.f., $p = 0.000$). In the Central System the percentage of *brachycerca* females ranged from 100 to 80.3 % (Table 2), decreasing significantly in the E-W direction ($r^2 = -0.669$, $p = 0.013$, Fig. 3). However, the correlation of this percentage was non-significant with mean annual temperature ($r^2 = 0.079$, $p = 0.497$) and with annual precipitation ($r^2 = 0.294$, $p = 0.164$). In male exuviae, by contrast, *typica* percentages did not differ between the Cantabrian Mountains and Central System (98.8 and 98.2 %, respectively, $\chi^2 = 0.033$, 1 d.f., $p = 0.854$). Within the Central System, the percentage of *brachycerca* did not vary significantly with E-W longitude ($r^2 = -0.352$, $p = 0.391$).

Figure 3. West coordinate (expressed in decimal degrees) and percentage of female *Boyeria irene* exuviae of the *brachycerca* form in rivers from the Central System of the Iberian Peninsula (4 – Zêzere; 5 – Frío; 6 – Agadón; 7 – Ladrillar; 8 – Francia; 9 – Tormes; 10 – Alberche; 11 – Eresma).

Table 2. Percentage of *brachycerca* (B) and *typica* (T) forms in male and female exuviae of *Boyeria irene* collected in three rivers from Cantabrian Mountains and eight rivers from Central System. n – sample size. Indet – indeterminate.

	River	n	Males			Females		
			B	T	Indet	n	B	T
Cantabrian Mountains	1 Cova	138	0.7	99.3	0	184	99.5	0.5
	2 Tuela	12	0	100	0	40	97.5	2.5
	3 Sabor	12	8.3	91.7	0	23	100	0
Central System	4 Zézere	70	0	100	0	132	80.3	19.7
	5 Frío	44	4.5	88.7	6.8	64	93.8	6.2
	6 Agadón	63	11.1	85.7	3.2	55	87.3	12.7
	7 Ladrillar	46	2.2	97.8	0	62	95.2	4.8
	8 Francia	283	0.4	99.6	0	293	93.2	6.8
	9 Tormes	21	0	95.2	4.8	30	96.7	3.3
	10 Alberche	39	0	100	0	80	100	0
	11 Eresma	39	0	100	0	46	97.8	2.2

Discussion

The presence of female *Boyeria irene* of the *brachycerca* and *typica* forms has long been known (e.g., NAVÁS 1919; WENGER 1959), but to date the relative frequency of the two forms has not been quantified. The values of CEL form two discrete groups, separated by a gap (at 1.5 mm), which therefore could be used to distinguish between *forma brachycerca* and *f. typica*. The CEL/PAL ratio proved valid as a way of identifying females of the *brachycerca* form but did not coincide with the value of the CEL in a large percentage of females of the *typica* form. Length of the paraproct relative to the length of the other body structures is a great help for identifying the species correctly (LANDWER & SITES 2005), and this is also true in *B. irene* (MÜLLER et al. 2012; NUNES et al. 2021). It therefore appears legitimate to use the CEL/PAL ratio to identify the forms. However, using these two traits (CEL and CEL/PAL ratio) the status of a small percentage (0.6% of the total number) of females remained ambiguous.

To date, males of *B. irene* have been assigned to the *typica* form (WENGER 1959). In the present study, the measurement of cerci has shown the existence of a few males of the *brachycerca* form, together with the existence of intermediate sizes between *brachycerca* and *typica*. Therefore, quantifying the length of cerci is necessary to know the importance of dimorphism. Both the CEL/PAL ratio and the CEL value allow reliable identification of females, although this is less reliable in males. However, it is necessary to check whether the value of CEL = 1.5 mm found here as a point of separation of the two forms is also valid for other populations.

The data published so far on the frequency of the *brachycerca* and *typica* forms show a high variability according to geographical areas (JACQUEMIN 1985; MIKOLAJEWSKI et al. 2000). Our data show that over a mountain range (Central System) and with a large sample size it is possible to show a geographical variation of the two forms of *B. irene*: In the area of the Iberian Peninsula here studied, the *typica* form becomes more abundant towards the west. In geographical areas further south, the percentage of the *typica* form is high (14.8–23.6%; FERRERAS-ROMERO & SUHLING 2021), not so much in southern Portugal (7.1%; SANTOS LOUREIRO 2014), but in Morocco (61.5% *typica*, but n = 13 females; JACQUEMIN 1985). In south-western France, *f. brachycerca* ranged from 50 to 88% (MIKOLAJEWSKI et al. 2000), which confirms the high geographical variability of *B. irene*. Nonetheless, FERRERAS-ROMERO & SUHLING (2021) propose that a sample size of at least 15 female specimens (exuviae or larvae) is required for reliable results, and so new data are needed for some French populations. It would also be interesting to know the proportions of both *brachycerca* and *typica* forms in populations from central and eastern France as well as from Switzerland, where *B. irene* exclusively occurs in pre-Alpine lakes (HOESS 2005).

In summary, the criteria for identification of *B. irene* forms must be based on morphometric traits, and therefore cerci must be accurately measured. It seems particularly important to investigate males with short cerci, which occur at low frequency in some populations.

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